

1 **Tribological performance of silicon nitride and carbon black**
2 **Ionanofluids based on 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium**
3 **methanesulfonate**

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11 **Abstract**

12 Development of nano-lubricants by the dispersion of nano-particles in current lubricants has contributed to improving energy
13 efficiency reducing wear and friction. During the last two decades, ionic liquids have evolved as novel lubricants or lubricant
14 additives, especially for high vacuum and high temperature. Nevertheless, the number of experimental studies regarding the
15 tribological properties of Ionanofluids, defined as dispersions of nano-particles in ionic liquids, is limited. 1-ethyl-3-
16 methylimidazolium methanesulfonate, [EMIM][MS], is a promising candidate for lubrication applications due to its wide liquid
17 range, high thermal conductivity, low friction coefficients and low compressibility in comparison with commercial mineral and
18 synthetic hydrocarbon based lubricants. In this work, Ionanofluid lubricants based on dispersions of nano-additives (silicon
19 nitride and carbon black) at mass concentration between 0.10 to 1.0 wt% in [EMIM][MS] were designed. The nearly spherical
20 morphology of the nano-additives, silicon nitride and carbon black, was described by using scanning electron microscopy. The
21 stabilities of the resulting nano-particle dispersions in ionic liquids were analyzed by dynamic light scattering measurements of
22 size for one month. Tribological characterization was performed by a rotational rheometer coupled with a tribology cell with
23 ball-on-three-pins configuration (100Cr6 steel) in sliding conditions at 298.15 and 353.15 K. Afterwards, the wear track
24 morphology of the worn pins was analyzed by a 3D optical profiler and Raman Spectroscopy. The dispersions at the optimal
25 nano-additive concentrations for lubrication reached friction coefficient decreases of up to 16% and wear tracks with a volume
26 28 times lower. Additionally, the density and dynamic viscosity of [EMIM][MS] and the optimal Ionanofluids for lubrication
27 applications measured with a rotational Stabinger visco-densimeter in the 278.15 to 373.15 K temperature range show small
28 increases with almost no dependence on temperature.

29 **Keywords**

30 tribological properties; 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methanesulfonate; friction; Ionanofluids; nanolubricants.

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Nanofluids, dispersions of nano-sized solid particles in a conventional fluid, were initially conceived as a solution to enhance
 33 the thermal properties of classic heat transfer fluids [1, 2]. Nevertheless, the use of nano-particles as additives has also contributed
 34 to improving the tribological efficiency of common lubricants [3, 4]. Several studies have experimentally verified important
 35 reductions of the friction coefficient and wear volume by dispersing diverse nano-materials (metals, oxides, nitrides, carbon-
 36 based structures) in conventional lubricants in the past decade, as summarized various recent reviews [4-6]. Singh et al [6]
 37 summarized the physical phenomena described in the literature to improve the lubrication performance of the base fluid by the
 38 nano-particle addition: rolling mechanism, mending mechanism, polishing mechanism and protective film (Figure 1). Rolling
 39 effect assumes that nano-additives work like ball bearings, rolling between the two solid surfaces. Mending effect considers that
 40 the nano-additives fill the small grooves and repair microdamages of friction surfaces. Polishing mechanism considers that hard
 41 nano-additives act as polishers by eliminating asperities, hence, diminishing surface roughness. Finally, protective film effect
 42 assumes that nano-particles create a lubricating layer on the friction surface, preventing the direct contact between metallic
 43 elements [6, 7].

44

45 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagram representing the lubrication physical phenomenon and the lubrication mechanisms of nano-
 46 particles as additives.

47 Ionic liquids, IL, are organic salts in liquid state composed only of ions and with melting points lower than 100 °C [8]. Those
 48 called room-temperature ILs melt below room-temperature. Their low melting points and negligible vapor pressure made them
 49 revolutionary in industry. They can be found in several applications such as heat transfer, absorption, sealant, lubricant or
 50 pressure transmission agents [9]. Specifically over the last two decades, ILs have been examined as novel lubricants [10] or
 51 lubricant additives [11, 12] due to their greater thermal stability, broader liquid range, lower volatility, lower flammability, higher
 52 thermal conductivity, and lower sensitivity to environmental variations in rheological behavior than conventional lubricants,
 53 among other interesting characteristics [12, 13]. ILs have been considered adequate as lubricants for extreme environments such
 54 as high vacuum and high temperature. Moreover, some ILs may constitute an environmental and health friendly alternative in
 55 comparison to traditional anti-wear additives (ZDDP) [13, 14].

56 The combination of the concepts of nanofluid and ionic liquid leads to the idea of Ionanofluids, which can be defined as
57 dispersions of nano-particles in ionic liquids. This term was first proposed in 2009 [15] and since then, the scientific concern
58 about these nano-dispersions has continuously increased [16, 17], mainly being used as heat transfer fluids [18, 19]. Nevertheless,
59 many of the favorable lubrication mechanisms and properties described for both nanofluids (potential rolling, mending, polishing
60 and protective film effects) and ionic liquids (protective film, interesting thermal and rheological properties, high vacuum and
61 temperature adequacy, less harmful alternative for the environment and health) can show promising synergistic results.

62 There are few studies in the literature regarding the use of Ionanofluids for lubrication. Concerning studies examining
63 Ionanofluids directly as lubricating agents, some literature examples and their main conclusions are summarized as follows.
64 Initially, different authors [20-23] used ILs with hexafluorophosphate (PF_6) and tetrafluoroborate (BF_4) anions, but their
65 reactivity with water produces corrosive hydrogen fluoride, so the applicability of these Ionanofluids as lubricants is restricted
66 [24-26]. Khare et al. [27] synthesized and tribologically characterized at room temperature two different dispersions of graphene
67 in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium iodide, [BMIM][I], obtaining slight reductions of the friction coefficient, wear, and roughness
68 surface, in comparison to the neat IL. These behaviors were attributed to three main mechanisms: rolling, sliding, and exfoliation
69 and film effects. The authors conclude that the rolling (due to nano-particles) and sliding (due to aggregates) phenomena compete
70 between them when aggregates begin to appear and that the ball rolling effect is less effective for square-shaped nano-particles
71 than for spherical nano-particles. Kheireddin et al. [28] studied the tribological properties at room temperature of SiO_2 nano-
72 particles as additives of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium (trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide, [BMIM][TFSI], observing that the best
73 anti-friction and anti-wear behavior were achieved for the optimum NP concentration (0.05 wt%), with a wear reduction of 24%.
74 These improvements were ascribed to the enhanced loading capacity of the IL by the presence of SiO_2 nano-particles and to the
75 capacity of the nano-particles to fill valleys between asperities (polishing mechanism). Yegin et al. [29] investigated the
76 tribological behavior at room temperature of functionalized SiO_2 dispersions in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium
77 bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide, [BMIM][NTf₂], reaching the higher friction coefficient reduction, 37%, for the 0.1 wt%
78 concentration. This enhancement was attributed to the roller bearing effect of spherical SiO_2 nano-particles. Carrión et al. [30]
79 and Espejo et al. [31] analyzed the tribological properties at room temperature of 0.5 wt% single-walled CNT and 0.5 wt% multi-
80 walled CNT in 1-octyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ([OMIM][Cl]) and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tosylate
81 ([EMIM][TOS]), respectively. These authors obtained negligible wear surfaces and friction coefficients, with great reductions
82 of 66 and 54% with respect to neat IL, respectively. These reductions were attributed to the improved load-carrying capacity of
83 the dispersion and its enhanced ability to separate the sliding surfaces (explained by the interactions between nano-additives and
84 IL molecules). From the same group, Saurín et al. [23, 32] obtained tribological characterizations at room temperature for 0.1
85 wt% few layer graphene and 0.1 wt% nano-diamonds dispersions in protic ammonium carboxylate tri-[bis(2-
86 hydroxyethylammonium)] citrate [32]. Graphene dispersion led to slight reductions of the IL friction coefficient for full-fluid
87 and thin layer lubrication, while nano-diamond dispersions lead to a 30% reduction. The graphene-IL dispersion covers the
88 sliding path with a protecting layer that prevents wear, whereas this anti-wear effect is not observed for nano-diamonds. Besides,
89 Pamies et al. [33] studied the tribological performance of 0.5 to 1 wt% graphene dispersions in [EMIM] dicyanamide ([DCA])
90 and [EMIM][TFSI] at room temperature. They obtained maximum reductions of 11 and 40% in friction and wear, respectively,
91 for [EMIM][DCA], and a maximum friction reduction of 11% for [EMIM][TFSI]. The higher lubrication was attributed to three
92 main reasons: the superior load-carrying ability of the dispersions, the formation of a surface layer of graphene deposited on the

93 wear track, and the ability of graphene sheets to retain the nano-sized wear debris, preventing the creation of larger abrasive
94 agglomerates.

95 As observed, the literature of Ionanofluids for lubrication applications usually describe tribological properties at room
96 conditions. Therefore, comprehensive experimental analyses are needed to evaluate the effect of temperature variation.
97 Moreover, most of the research on Ionanofluid lubricants has focused on the use of halogen-containing ionic liquids, which can
98 cause negative effects on the environment [8, 34]. The delay in the development of industrial applications of the very promising
99 research results obtained with Ionanofluid lubricants could be attributed to several factors, one of the most relevant is doubtless
100 the problems of agglomeration of the nano-particles [34, 35], which can change the lubrication regime and increase wear due to
101 abrasion. For this reason, as Avilés et al. [34] pointed out, there is an urgent need to optimize the nano-additive concentration,
102 not only to achieve long-term stability, but also to control its influence on the thermophysical and tribochemical properties of the
103 nanofluid. Hence, the aim of this work is to obtain the optimal concentration of two nano-additives for a non-halogenated ionic
104 liquid, analyzing the tribological and thermophysical behavior at different temperatures.

105 The non-halogenated IL 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methanesulfonate, [EMIM][MS], has been chosen due to the much
106 lower isothermal compressibility and lower friction coefficients than those of commercial hydraulic fluids and compressor
107 lubricants [36]. Furthermore, its thermal conductivity, $0.20 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ at 273 K [37], is higher than that usually reported for
108 mineral and synthetic hydrocarbon based lubricants, $0.14 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ at 273 K [38], which implies a greater capacity to dissipate
109 heat, one of the main functions of the lubricants. Recently, Bioucas et al. [37] concluded that the chemical structure and
110 intermolecular interactions that characterize this IL lead to exceptional properties, which allow for heat transfer, among other
111 applications. In addition, [EMIM][MS] has a wide liquid temperature range, with its freezing point at around 250 K [39]. The
112 value of its kinematic viscosity at 313 K has been reported as 54.4 cSt [40].

113 To the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no previous experimental works in the literature analyzing the performance
114 of [EMIM][MS] as a novel lubricant. In this work, the friction coefficient in sliding conditions between steel surfaces and the
115 corresponding wear tracks of [EMIM][MS] were analyzed at two different controlled temperatures, 298.15 and 353.15 K, to
116 study the temperature dependence. Furthermore, silicon nitride and carbon black, two nano-additives with different promising
117 characteristics to improve the tribological performance of a lubricant and a relatively low production cost, have been employed
118 to design [EMIM][MS]. Silicon nitride nano-particles are characterized by their resistance to oxidation at high temperatures,
119 wear, and corrosion resistance. In addition, Çöl et al. [41] have found that silicon nitride nano-particles reduce the friction
120 coefficient of an engine oil up to around 30% for 0.8 wt % concentration and the specific worn rate up to 40% for 0.1 wt%
121 concentration. Ionanofluids in the 0.10 to 1.0 wt% concentration range. The appearance of the optimal concentration for each
122 nano-additive and the different physical mechanisms involved in the improvement of tribological performance is one of the
123 objectives of this work. Moreover, the morphology of the nano-additives and the stability of the resulting dispersions were
124 analyzed. Then, the Ionanofluid lubricants were tribologically characterized, analyzing the friction coefficient at 298.15 and
125 353.15 K and characterizing the corresponding wear tracks. Elemental mapping and Raman spectra of the worn surfaces
126 contributed to the physical interpretation. Additionally, the density and dynamic viscosity of the base IL and the optimized nano-
127 additive dispersion for lubrication applications were also experimentally determined in a wide temperature range.

128 **2. Materials and methods**129 *2.1. Design*

130 The ionic liquid 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methanesulfonate, [EMIM][MS], was provided by Merck (Darmstadt,
 131 Germany) with a purity $\geq 95\%$ and a water content < 0.5 wt%, see Table 1. Silicon nitride, Si_3N_4 , and carbon black, CB, were
 132 provided by PlasmaChem (Berlin, Germany) with purities $> 99\%$, see Table 1. The Ionanofluid lubricants, dispersions of Si_3N_4
 133 and CB at three mass concentrations (0.10, 0.25 and 1.0 wt%) in [EMIM][MS], were prepared following a two-step method. The
 134 amounts of IL and each nano-additive used were weighted in a CPA225 balance from Sartorius AG (Goettingen, Germany) with
 135 0.1 mg uncertainty. Subsequently, the dispersions were sonicated through an ultrasonic bath Fisherbrand FB11201 from Thermo
 136 Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA) for 120 min, operating in continuous shaking mode with an effective power of 180 W
 137 and a sonication frequency of 37 kHz.

138 **Table 1.** Main characteristics of materials used, according to the manufacturer^{1,2}.

Ionic liquid	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methanesulfonate¹, [EMIM][MS]
CAS Number	145022-45-3
Other common nomenclature	[EMIM] [MeSO ₃] [EMIM] [CH ₃ SO ₃] [C2MIM][MS] [C ₂ mim][CH ₃ SO ₃]
Chemical structure	
	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$
Flash point	559.15 K
Purity	$\geq 95\%$
Water content	< 0.5 wt%
Nano-additive	Silicon nitride², Si_3N_4
Average particle size	25 nm
Specific surface area	75 $\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$
Purity	$> 99\%$
Other contents	Fe < 0.05 , Ca < 0.05 , Al $< 0.1\%$
Nano-additive	Carbon black², CB
Average particle size	13 nm
Specific surface area	550 m^2/g
Purity	$> 99\%$
Other contents	Ash $< 0.02\%$

139 ¹Merck (Darmstadt, Germany)140 ²PlasmaChem (Berlin, Germany)141 *2.2. Experimental*

142 The nano-particles used were morphologically characterized through scanning electron microscopy (SEM). A drop of each
 143 dispersion composed of each nano-powder in analytical grade methanol was dried at room temperature on a silica support.

144 Backscattering electron images over the specimens were obtained by a JEOL JSM-6700F field emission scanning electron
145 microscope from JEOL (Tokyo, Japan) at an operating accelerator voltage of 10.0 kV.

146 The stability of the ionic dispersions was analyzed by dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique through a Zetasizer Nano
147 ZS from Malvern Instruments (Malvern, United Kingdom). The temporal evolution of the apparent size of the nano-additives
148 was characterized with the procedure previously described [42, 43]. The present study was carried out for the 0.25 wt%
149 Ionanofluids, the least concentrated dispersions, for 31 days at 298.15 K with a scattering angle of 173°. Two types of samples
150 were analyzed: dispersions in static conditions since their preparation (from now on referred to as “static” samples) and
151 dispersions to which mechanical agitation was applied before the DLS measurement (from now on referred to as “shaken”
152 samples). The mechanical agitation of the shaken samples was performed with a ZX3 Advanced Vortex Mixer from VELP
153 Scientifica (Usmate Velate, Italy) during 1 min at 2000 rpm.

154 The tribological characterization was conducted by a rotational rheometer MCR 302 from Anton Paar (Graz, Austria)
155 coupled with a tribology cell T-PTD 200 at 298.15 and 353.15 K [44, 45]. The temperature was controlled with a Peltier system
156 H-PTD 200 with 0.1 K accuracy. A ball-on-three-pins configuration was employed for the tests. The 100Cr6 steel ball is 12.7
157 mm in diameter and the 100Cr6 steel pins have a diameter of 6 mm and are 6 mm high. Before each test, all materials were
158 cleaned by means of hexane and dried in atmospheric conditions. 1.3 mL of sample per test was used, ball and pins being
159 completely submerged. The operating parameters were 45 N total axial force of the rheometer (21.20 N normal force at each pin-
160 ball surface contact, 0.7 GPa average contact pressure), 0.1 m·s⁻¹ constant sliding velocity and 340 m sliding distance. Three
161 replicates were run for each dispersion. More information about the tribological cell and the procedure can be found elsewhere
162 [44, 45].

163 The surface morphology of the worn pins generated after the tribological tests was analyzed by a 3D optical profiler S neox
164 from Sensofar (Tarrasa, Spain) [46, 47]. 3D images of the wear of the pins as well as the wear scar diameter, the wear track depth
165 and wear hole volume were obtained in confocal mode with a 10x objective. This apparatus was also used to evaluate the
166 roughness (Ra) of the worn surfaces of the pins lubricated with the studied samples. For this task, the ISO4287 standard
167 (International Organization for Standardization, Vernier, Switzerland) was followed, employing a Gaussian filter with a long
168 wavelength cut-off of 0.08 mm and 0.25 mm. The presented values of wear scar diameter, the wear track depth, wear hole volume
169 and roughness were obtained as the average of the three replicates for each nano-additive concentration. Elemental mapping and
170 Raman spectra of the worn surfaces were recorded with a confocal Raman microscope alpha 300R+ from WITec (Ulm, Germany)
171 at a wavelength of 532 nm in order to obtain information about the composition in the wear track.

172 Dynamic viscosities were determined by a rotational Stabinger viscometer SVM 3000 from Anton Paar (Graz, Austria) at
173 atmospheric pressure and in the temperature range from 278.15 to 373.15 K, 5 K step. This device also includes a vibrating tube
174 densimeter that determines the densities at the same conditions. More information of this setup was previously described [48,
175 49]. The expanded uncertainty of these measurements (0.95 level of confidence) was previously established as 1% for dynamic
176 viscosity, 0.5 kg·m⁻³ for density and 0.02 K for the temperature.

177 **3. Results**178 *3.1. Nano-powder characterization and Ionanofluid stability*

179 SEM images of Si₃N₄ and CB nano-powders (Figure 2) indicate that both types of nano-particles present a nearly spherical
180 shape. The creation of the observed aggregates can be attributed to the drying process. The perceived particle sizes are in
181 agreement with the information provided by the manufacturer (Table 1), with Si₃N₄ nano-particles being about twice as large as
182 CB nano-particles.

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Figure 2. SEM images of Si₃N₄ (a) and CB (b) nano-particles at $\times 100000$ magnification

185 With regard to the stability characterization, it is worth mentioning that the size value by DLS measurements is assumed as
186 the diameter of a perfect sphere that presents a translational diffusion coefficient equal to that of the dispersed particle. Thus,
187 these values are commonly referred to as hydrodynamic diameter or apparent size. On the other hand, the average Z-size is the
188 intensity-weighted mean size calculated from a cumulants fit of the intensity autocorrelation function resulting from the DLS
189 measurement. Therefore, it should be taken into account that the stability analysis is focused on the temporal evolution of the
190 DLS measurements rather than the values of the sizes themselves. Figure 2 shows the average Z-size dependence on time after
191 preparation for “static” and “shaken” 0.25 wt% Ionanofluids.

Figure 3. Average Z-size dependence on time after preparation at 298.15 K for the 0.25 wt% dispersions: Si₃N₄ Ionanofluids (a) and CB Ionanofluids (b). Error bars mean standard deviation (k=2) of the experimental measurements and reference lines (---) indicate the calculated average value for each sample.

Figure 3 a) indicates a quasi-constant average Z-size value during one month for “static” (~ 103 nm) and “shaken” (~ 113 nm) Si₃N₄ Ionanofluids, which is a sign of the excellent long-term stability of the dispersions. Furthermore, it should be noted that the differences between the obtained values are covered by the experimental expanded uncertainty. On the other hand, Figure 3 b) shows a marked decrease of the average Z-size with time for the “static” CB Ionanofluid while a practically constant value for the “shaken” CB Ionanofluid (~ 286 nm) during the one-month period is obtained. From these results we conclude that the largest dispersed CB nano-particles or particle agglomeration tend to precipitate in static conditions, but the initial dispersion state is easily recoverable by means of a brief mechanical agitation.

3.2. Tribological characterization

A first tribological test was performed for the six designed dispersions and the IL, in order to characterize the nano-additive mass concentration dependence on the friction coefficient, μ . Figure 4 gathers the experimental friction coefficients as a function of the sliding distance for all the samples at 353.15 K, showing that both 0.25 wt% Ionanofluid lubricants reach the highest friction coefficient reduction among those analyzed. This decrease is higher for the 0.25 wt% CB dispersion (0.089 average value, 16 % decrease) than for the 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ dispersion (0.097 average value, 8.5 % decrease), as is also shown in Table 2 and Figure 5. Both 0.10 wt% samples (Si₃N₄ and CB-based Ionanofluids) exhibit practically the same friction behavior than the IL (an average μ value of 0.106 for [EMIM][MS] while average μ values of 0.105 and 0.103 for the corresponding Si₃N₄ and CB-based Ionanofluids, respectively). The 1.0 wt% CB dispersion presents an average μ value of 0.105, very similar to that of the IL (0.106), while the 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ dispersion shows an average μ value of 0.123, which implies a 16 % worsening with respect to the neat IL.

The existence of an optimal nano-additive concentration for which a minimum friction coefficient is achieved was previously pointed out for other nano-lubricants [20, 21, 28, 29, 33, 46, 47, 50]. For instance, Pamies et al.[33] analyzed the tribological

216 behavior of [EMIM][DCA] and [EMIM][TFSI] Ionanofluids, using few-layers graphene as nano-additive in the 0.5 to 1.0 wt%
217 concentration range. They reported the highest friction reductions in comparison to the ILs for the 0.5 wt% nano-additive
218 concentration, the lowest analyzed. Çöl et al. [41] also found an optimal friction value for dispersions of silicon nitride nano-
219 particles in an engine oil at 0.8 wt % concentration. This friction behavior could be explained because at lower concentrations,
220 the base oil effect governs the friction performance since the quantity of nano-particles at the contact surface is not enough to
221 prevent wear. Meanwhile, when the nano-particle concentration is too high, nano-particle deposition can create new asperities
222 and therefore increase the friction. In order to confirm this hypothesis, the roughness (R_a) of the worn surfaces of the lubricated
223 pins were plotted in Figure 5 together with the friction coefficients at a function of the concentration. Both properties have
224 minima for the dispersion of 0.25 wt% nano-additive. Thus, 75 % and 61% reductions with respect to the IL are obtained in the
225 roughness of the worn track when the pins are lubricated with 0.25 wt% CB and Si_3N_4 Ionanofluids, respectively. Average R_a
226 values are also given in Table 3. The reductions of the roughness and friction coefficients for the 0.25 wt% concentration show
227 that polishing and mending effects occur due to the presence of nano-particles. The reduction of the friction coefficient can also
228 be due to the rolling effect owing to the cuasi-sphericity of both types of nano-particles. In the case of CB Ionanofluids, the
229 highest roughness reduction may be due to their small nano-particle size (13 nm) compared to Si_3N_4 (25 nm). On the other hand,
230 when the concentration increases up to 1 wt% worn surface roughness is only 20% (CB) and 9% (Si_3N_4) lower than those
231 obtained with those corresponding to the neat IL showing that polishing and mending effects are negatively compensated by
232 other effects. From Figure 5 it can be concluded that 0.25 wt% of Si_3N_4 and CB Ionanofluids provide the best performance
233 between the studied dispersions. When the concentration is lower or higher than 0.25 wt%, the friction and roughness reductions
234 are weakened. That may be ascribed to the competitive adsorption between the additive particles and the IL. When the additive
235 concentration is low, the particles adsorbed on the contact regions are insufficient and even serve as abrasive elements to damage
236 the mating metal surfaces [51]. When concentration increases, more nano-particles are adsorbed onto the contact surfaces, the
237 boundary lubricating film becomes thicker and firmer to prevent the asperities of the mating surfaces from direct contact, thus
238 the friction and roughness decrease. Nevertheless, if the concentration increases further, many particles and aggregates are
239 delivered onto the contact areas leading to aggregation increase at the friction interfaces due to friction force, which in turn
240 causes the friction process to be unstable (as seen in Figure 4) and local breakage of oil film, which results in higher friction and
241 roughness. Thus, big aggregates may scratch the surface under loading and form abrasive clusters (new asperities) between the
242 sliding surfaces, resulting in an increase of wear [52]. In the case of Si_3N_4 these last effects are stronger because these nano-
243 particles are harder than CB nano-particles.

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Figure 4. Friction coefficient, μ , as a function of the sliding distance at 353.15 K for [EMIM][MS] and 0.10, 0.25 and 1.0 wt% dispersions of Si_3N_4 (a) and CB (b).

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Figure 5. Average friction coefficient, μ , and Roughness parameter, Ra , as a function of the nano-additive concentration at 353.15 K.

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Table 2. Roughness parameters, Ra , and the corresponding uncertainties of worn surfaces lubricated with [EMIM][MS], Si_3N_4 and CB Ionanofluids at 293.15 K (Gaussian filter of 0.08 mm) and 353.15 K (Gaussian filter of 0.25 mm).

T [K]	Lubricant	Ra / nm
293.15	[EMIM][MS]	25.9 (± 2.4)
	0.10 wt% Si_3N_4	24.7 (± 2.6)
	0.25 wt% Si_3N_4	21.4 (± 2.2)
	1 wt% Si_3N_4	25.3 (± 2.3)
	0.10 wt% CB	21.3 (± 2.2)
	0.25 wt% CB	18.3 (± 1.8)
	1 wt% CB	22.4 (± 1.7)
353.15	[EMIM][MS]	179 (± 13)
	0.10 wt% Si_3N_4	122 (± 7.9)
	0.25 wt% Si_3N_4	68.5 (± 5.6)
	1 wt% Si_3N_4	162 (± 15)
	0.10 wt% CB	111 (± 6.6)
	0.25 wt% CB	44.7 (± 4.5)
	1 wt% CB	143 (± 11)

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Taking into account the previous experimental results, attention will subsequently be paid to the optimal Ionanofluids in terms of friction coefficient reduction, i.e. 0.25 wt% of Si_3N_4 and CB-based dispersions. Figure 6 and Table 3 show the friction coefficient reductions obtained by these selected dispersions at 293.15 and 353.15 K. Decreases of the friction coefficient of up to 24 % were obtained for the base fluid lowering the temperature 60 K. This behavior and the decrease in fluctuations can be explained because when the temperature decreases the viscosity increases and the lubrication film becomes wider. The following comparison between friction coefficients, μ , can be established at both temperatures: $\mu_{0.25 \text{ wt\% CB}} < \mu_{0.25 \text{ wt\% } Si_3N_4} < \mu_{[EMIM][MS]}$. It should be noted that the noticeable decreases in the friction coefficient found for both proposed Ionanofluids at 353.15 K are maintained at 293.15 K, but those reductions fall by half at the lower temperature.

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Figure 6. Friction coefficient, μ , as a function of the sliding distance for [EMIM][MS] and for 0.25 wt% Ionanofluids at 293.15 K and 353.15 K.

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Table 3. Average values of friction coefficient, μ , and wear scar diameter, WSD, wear track depth, WTD, and wear hole volume, WHV, as a maximum (the respective standard deviations are shown between brackets) for [EMIM][MS], 0.25 wt% Si_3N_4 Ionanofluid and 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid at 293.15 and 353.15 K.

T [K]	Lubricant	μ	WSD [μm]	WTD [μm]	WHV [$10^3\mu\text{m}^3$]
293.15	[EMIM][MS]	0.081 (± 0.003)	300 (± 7.5)	0.23 (± 0.02)	10.3 (± 0.3)
	0.25 wt% Si_3N_4	0.077 (± 0.003)	334 (± 9.3)	0.94 (± 0.06)	13.1 (± 0.5)
	0.25 wt% CB	0.074 (± 0.004)	247 (± 5.8)	0.44 (± 0.04)	10.0 (± 0.3)
353.15	[EMIM][MS]	0.106 (± 0.004)	777 (± 20)	10.9 (± 0.47)	1951 (± 64.7)
	0.25 wt% Si_3N_4	0.097 (± 0.005)	499 (± 12)	2.98 (± 0.18)	159 (± 5.7)
	0.25 wt% CB	0.089 (± 0.003)	421 (± 14)	1.60 (± 0.10)	68 (± 3)

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Figure 7. 3D profiles (a, b, c) and 2D images (d, e, f) of the wear tracks at 353.15 K, 10x magnification, for [EMIM][MS] (a, d), 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionanofluid (b, e) and 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid (c, f).

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Figure 8. Cross section profiles of the wear tracks with the corresponding wear scar diameters (WSD) at 353.15 K for [EMIM][MS] (a), 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionanofluid (b) and 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid (c).

275 As presented in Table 3, the obtained wears at the lowest temperature are very similar for all lubricants in terms of wear scar
 276 diameter, WSD, wear track depth, WTD, or wear hole volume, WHV. Contrarily, these values at the highest temperature are
 277 much lower for the Ionanofluids than for the base IL, as Figures 7 and 8 specifically show. In particular, reductions of 46 and
 278 85% were achieved for the pins lubricated with the 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid in WSD and WTD, respectively (being the mean
 279 WHV more than 28 times lower). As regards pins lubricated with 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionanofluid, reductions of 36 and 73% in WSD
 280 and WTD, respectively, were obtained (WHV more than 12 times lower).

281 The elemental mapping and Raman spectra of the worn surfaces lubricated with the 0.25 wt% CB and 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄
 282 Ionanofluids were carried out to identify the role that the nano-particles and ionic liquid play in the reduction of the surface wear
 283 of the pins. As it is presented in Figure 9, an important tribofilm is evidenced due to a significant presence of IL (blue color) in
 284 the mapping of the worn surfaces lubricated with both nanolubricants. The IL contains “aromatic” C–H units with distinctive
 285 stretching modes associated to peaks between 3070–3200 cm⁻¹ and it has characteristic bands in the region 1450–1570 cm⁻¹ and
 286 at about 1150–1370 cm⁻¹ [53]. As regards the methanesulfonate anion the characteristic Raman frequencies are assigned to
 287 symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations, $\nu_s(\text{SO}_3)$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{SO}_3)$, between 1050 and 1200cm⁻¹ [53].

288 Moreover, a clear presence of CB nano-particles appears on the worn surface lubricated with 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid
 289 (Figure 9b), these nano-additives are placed along several furrows on the worn surface. Characteristic peaks of CB nano-particles
 290 are identified in the Raman spectrum of worn surface: carbon black generally exhibits two broad and strongly overlapping peaks
 291 with intensity maxima at around 1350 cm⁻¹ and around 1585 cm⁻¹, which are associated to the defect band (D band) and the
 292 graphite band (G band) [54, 55]. The presence of CB nano-particles as well as the reduction in roughness could indicate the
 293 occurrence of mending effect due to the CB nano-particles. Regarding the worn surface lubricated with 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄
 294 Ionanofluid, no physical adsorption of the nano-particles is observed (Figure 9a). Therefore, the wear reduction may be mainly
 295 due to rolling and the polishing effects because of the nearly spherical shape and high hardness of Si₃N₄ nano-particles,
 296 respectively.

297

298

299 **Figure 9.** Raman spectra and elemental map of the worn surface obtained with the 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionomerfluid (a) and the 0.25
300 wt% CB Ionomerfluid (b).

301 3.3. Density and dynamic viscosity

302 Figure 10a shows that experimental density values for [EMIM][MS] (reported in Table 4) are in agreement with the
303 corresponding literature data [37, 40, 56-68], with absolute average deviations within 0.4%. It should be noted that the content
304 of water is slightly different among the reported literature, but always less than 1% [37, 40, 56-68]. The best agreements were
305 found with the data from Domanska et al. [60], Rabari et al. [64], Krannich et al. [40], Marium et al. [66], and Chereches et al.
306 [68], with absolute average deviations of 0.03%, 0.10%, 0.09%, 0.02% and 0.05%, respectively.

307

308 **Figure 10.** Relative deviations between experimental, *exp*, and literature, *lit*, data as a function of temperature for
309 [EMIM][MS] for density, ρ , [37, 40, 56-68] (a), and dynamic viscosity, η , [37, 56, 58, 59, 65, 69-71] (b).

310 Table 4 shows the experimental density values of the optimal nano-additive loading dispersions for the friction reduction, the
 311 0.25 wt% Ionanofluids. The base fluid and both Ionanofluids show a density decrease of 5.0% with the temperature rising from
 312 278.15 to 373.15 K. On the other hand, the dispersion of Si₃N₄ and CB caused almost temperature independent increases in the
 313 densities around 0.14% and 0.10%, respectively. Increases in mass per unit volume can lead to additional difficulties in fluid
 314 flow. The reported density increases for the selected improved dispersions are less than 0.15% in both cases, a slight variation
 315 that does not involve a noticeable change in relation to the base fluid.

316 **Table 4.** Experimental densities, ρ , for [EMIM][MS], 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionanofluid and 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid at
 317 temperatures, T , from 278.15 to 373.15 K and fitting parameters, A_0 , A_1 , A_2 , standard deviations, s , and absolute average
 318 deviations, AAD, from Eq. (1).

T [K]	ρ [kg·m ⁻³]		
	[EMIM][MS]	0.25 wt% Si ₃ N ₄	0.25 wt% CB
278.15	1252.8	1254.9	1254.3
283.15	1249.3	1251.3	1250.7
288.15	1245.8	1247.9	1247.2
293.15	1242.5	1244.5	1243.8
298.15	1239.2	1241.1	1240.5
303.15	1236.0	1237.8	1237.2
308.15	1232.7	1234.5	1234.0
313.15	1229.5	1231.2	1230.7
318.15	1226.2	1227.9	1227.4
323.15	1222.9	1224.6	1224.1
328.15	1219.7	1221.2	1220.8
333.15	1216.4	1217.9	1217.5
338.15	1213.1	1214.6	1214.2
343.15	1209.8	1211.3	1210.9
348.15	1206.5	1208.0	1207.6
353.15	1203.2	1204.7	1204.3
358.15	1199.9	1201.4	1201.1
363.15	1196.7	1198.2	1197.8
368.15	1193.4	1194.9	1194.5
373.15	1190.2	1191.7	1191.3
A_0 [kg·m ⁻³]	1435.1	1439.1	1437.5
$-A_1$ [kg·m ⁻³ ·K ⁻¹]	0.6566	0.6636	0.6602
$10^9 \cdot A_2$ [kg·m ⁻³ ·K ⁻²]	2.824	5.891	7.324
s [kg·m ⁻³]	0.11	0.14	0.14
AAD	0.006%	0.008%	0.008%

319 The temperature dependence on density was correlated by the following quadratic equation:

320
$$\rho(T) = A_2 \cdot T^2 + A_1 \cdot T + A_0 \tag{1}$$

321 where ρ and T means density and temperature, respectively, and A_2 , A_1 and A_0 are the fitting parameters. The values of the fitting
 322 parameters reported in Table 4 allow for a correlation of the experimental density data with standard deviations lower than 0.15
 323 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for all samples. Isobaric thermal expansivity at atmospheric pressure was obtained by the following equation [72, 73]:

$$324 \quad \alpha_p = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{d\rho}{dT} \right)_p \quad (2)$$

325 Figure 11 gathers the obtained isobaric thermal expansivities in the temperature range from 283.15 to 368.15 K. Rises with
 326 the temperature increase of 4.7% were detected for base fluid and Ionanofluids. The nano-additive dispersion leads to higher
 327 thermal expansivity values. Increases for the 0.25 wt% Si_3N_4 and CB loadings of around 0.92 % and 0.45% were obtained,
 328 respectively. Isobaric thermal expansivity values are useful to determine the size of the container when the fluid is heated. As
 329 observed, the differences between Ionanofluids and base IL are lower than 1% in both cases.

330
 331 **Figure 11.** Isobaric thermal expansivity, α_p , as a function of temperature, T , for [EMIM][MS], 0.25 wt% Si_3N_4
 332 Ionanofluid and 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid.

333 Figure 10b shows the relative deviations between the experimental dynamic viscosities for [EMIM][MS] (Table 5) and the
 334 corresponding literature data [37, 56, 58, 59, 65, 69-71]. It should be noted that some data sets present large deviations from the
 335 rest of the literature data, with significant dependence on temperature. The absolute average deviations between the experimental
 336 dynamic viscosity data reported in this work and those from Tenney et al. [70] and Harris et al. [65] are within 4.2%. The best
 337 agreements were found with Hasse et al. [56], Bioucas et al. [37] and Safarov et al [71], with absolute average deviations of
 338 2.5%, 1.5% and 1.4%, respectively.

339 Table 5 also reports the experimental dynamic values of the optimal nano-additive loading dispersions for the friction
 340 reduction. The increasing temperature from 278.15 to 373.15 K leads to a dynamic viscosity reduction of 99% for [EMIM][MS]
 341 and both Ionanofluids. Contrastingly, increases in the ranges 3.5-6.3% and 5.2-12% at constant temperature were observed
 342 because of the dispersion of Si_3N_4 and CB in the base fluid, respectively. These increases tend to be lower as the temperature
 343 rises. Viscosity is directly related to the energy required to make a fluid flow. Small increases in dynamic viscosity were obtained
 344 for both selected Ionanofluids, where the increment for Si_3N_4 Ionanofluid is half of that for CB Ionanofluid. The CB dispersion,

345 which allows for a greater improvement in the friction coefficient and scar wear, implies a higher increase in viscosity and,
 346 therefore, a slightly higher pumping power.

347 **Table 5.** Experimental dynamic viscosities, η , for [EMIM][MS], 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionanofluid and 0.25 wt% CB
 348 Ionanofluid at temperatures, T , from 278.15 to 373.15 K and fitting parameters, η_0 , A and T_0 , standard deviations, s , and
 349 absolute average deviations, AAD, from Eq. (3).

T [K]	η [mPa·s]		
	[EMIM][MS]	0.25 wt% Si ₃ N ₄	0.25 wt% CB
278.15	689.8	732.9	772.3
283.15	439.7	465.6	492.0
288.15	295.0	311.0	329.6
293.15	206.2	216.7	230.1
298.15	149.1	156.2	166.2
303.15	111.1	116.1	123.5
308.15	84.98	88.59	94.26
313.15	66.49	69.15	73.52
318.15	53.07	55.09	58.43
323.15	43.07	44.67	47.26
328.15	35.51	36.78	38.82
333.15	29.70	30.73	32.29
338.15	25.13	26.01	27.19
343.15	21.50	22.26	23.14
348.15	18.57	19.23	19.91
353.15	16.19	16.77	17.28
358.15	14.22	14.73	15.11
363.15	12.59	13.05	13.32
368.15	11.22	11.64	11.82
373.15	10.06	10.44	10.58
η_0	0.2392	0.2339	0.2301
A [K]	3.447	3.492	3.608
T_0 [K]	194.1	194.0	192.6
s [mPa·s]	0.33	0.36	0.42
AAD	0.4%	0.9%	0.6%

350 The temperature dependence on the dynamic viscosity was correlated by the Vogel–Fulcher–Tammann (VFT) equation [74–
 351 76], or Vogel–Fulcher–Tammann–Hesse equation:

352
$$\eta = \eta_0 \cdot e^{\frac{A \cdot T_0}{T - T_0}} \tag{3}$$

353 where η and T means dynamic viscosity and temperature, respectively, and η_0 , A and T_0 are the fitting parameters. The values of
 354 the fitting parameters gathered in Table 5 allow for the correlation of the experimental dynamic viscosity data with absolute
 355 average deviations of less than 1%.

356 4. Conclusions

357 In this work the following features were achieved:

- 358 1. New Si₃N₄ and CB dispersions in [EMIM][MS] at nano-particle mass concentration between 0.1 to 1 % were
359 conveniently designed for lubrication purposes.
- 360 2. DLS measurements indicated the excellent long-term stability of the Si₃N₄ Ionanofluids and the easily recoverable initial
361 dispersion conditions of the CB Ionanofluids.
- 362 3. Ionanofluids at 0.25 wt% mass concentration achieved the highest friction coefficient reductions at both analyzed
363 temperatures, 293.15 and 353.15 K. At the highest temperature, these decreases reached 16% and 8.5% for the CB and
364 Si₃N₄ dispersions, respectively.
- 365 4. The maximum wear reductions were produced at 353.15K: the 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid achieved 46% and 85% in the
366 diameter and depth of the wear, respectively, whereas 36% and 73% reductions were respectively obtained for the 0.25
367 wt% Si₃N₄ Ionanofluid. The maximum volume reduction was achieved for the 0.25 wt% CB Ionanofluid with 28 times
368 lower wear volume than that for the base IL.
- 369 5. The roughness of the worn surfaces achieves 75% and 61% reductions by using the 0.25 wt% CB and Si₃N₄ new
370 lubricants, respectively.
- 371 6. Raman mapping indicates that mending effect occurs using the optimal CB Ionanofluid, but does not show this effect
372 for the optimal Si₃N₄ dispersion.
- 373 7. Dynamic viscosity rises lower or equal to 6.3% and 12% for the 0.25 wt% Si₃N₄ and CB Ionanofluids were reached,
374 whereas density increases up to around 0.14% and 0.10%, respectively, with almost no dependence on temperature.

375 CRediT authorship contribution statement

376 **Javier P. Vallejo**: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **José M. Liñeira del**
377 **Río**: Investigation, Methodology, Writing - original draft. **Josefa Fernández**: Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing - review &
378 editing. **Luis Lugo**: Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing - review & editing.

379 Declaration of competing interest

380 There is no conflict of interest.

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